

MECHANICAL CHARACTERISATION OF COMPOSITES WITH 3D-WOVEN REINFORCEMENT

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ABSTRACT

Flat specimens made of carbon/epoxy composite material are manufactured by resin transfer moulding, using 3D-woven carbon fibre preforms with a grid of warp yarns interlaced with both horizontal and vertical wefts. The aim of the study is to bring more light to the coupling between the mechanical properties of the composite material and the internal fibre architecture of its 3D-woven reinforcement. Factors that are varied in the fibre architecture are the amount of fibres in the through-thickness reinforcement (vertical weft) and the warp's wavelength.

Tensile, compressive, in-plane and out-of-plane shear and peel tests are performed for the mechanical characterisation. Tensile and compressive properties are found to decrease when the crimp of the warp yarns is increased, and even more so in compression. The in-plane shear strength is evaluated through use of a new test specimen, designed for the purpose. Results show that the strength is higher when the shear load is applied across the warp than across the weft, where the difference is attributed to varying fibre content in the two in-plane directions. The out-of-plane shear properties are compared through short beam shear tests and the inter-laminar shear strength (ILSS) is determined. It is shown that the ILSS increases with increasing yarn thickness in the vertical weft, which is intuitive. The peel strength is evaluated by the opening mode I interlaminar fracture toughness (G_{Ic}) through double cantilever beam tests. It is shown that G_{Ic} is greatly dependent on the amount of reinforcement in the vertical weft.

1 INTRODUCTION

Most fibre composite materials used today are composed of layers of fibre mats, weaves or tape, all having the fibres aligned in the same plane, thus constituting two-dimensional (2D) reinforcement. Such orientation is beneficial for the in-plane properties, but not for the out-of-plane properties, resulting in potential problems with delamination. To increase the out-of-plane properties fibres can be integrated in the out-of-plane direction, e.g. by three-dimensional (3D) weaving. In the 3D weaving loom, yarns in three principal directions are interlocked, allowing for direct manufacturing of complex preforms at net shape. However, the through-thickness-fibres bring about a certain trade-off, since the lower fraction of in-plane fibres reduces the (relative) in-plane properties. Weaving is also associated with a certain waviness of the fibres, which also reduces the in-plane mechanical performance.

3D textiles offer a virtually endless variation of architectures, where the most common ones are orthogonal interlocked, angle interlocked and layer-to-layer interlocked [1] fabrics. True 3D-weaving could however, according to Khokar [2], only be performed by interlacing a grid-like multiple-layer warp with sets of vertical and horizontal wefts. Such fully interlaced preforms have good structural integrity and the technology allows for a great variety of preform shapes.

Introducing out-of-plane fibres in the preforms makes the internal fibre architecture more complex and conventional laminate theory is then not applicable for predicting the mechanical properties of the material. There is a need to develop new methods for design and sizing of these materials and numerical and experimental studies are important to support such development. Although numerical models gradually become more accurate, experimental studies are essential, not only to determine material properties, but also to validate the numerical models. Numerous experimental studies have been

performed on this topic, but with focus on composites with preforms from orthogonal interlocked, angle interlocked, layer-to-layer interlocked fabrics [3-4], and not much on composites with fully interlaced 3D-woven reinforcement (3DW). However, Stig and Hallström [5] tested and compared 3DW to conventional 2D-reinforced composites. Results showed that the in-plane properties were lower but the out-of-plane properties higher for the 3DW than for 2D-reinforced composites. However, the size of the 3DW test specimens was limited by the production capacity at the time. The out-of-plane strength tests performed at the time were also unsuccessful since they failed to bring the 3DW specimens to the desired failure modes in the out-of-plane direction.

This paper presents results from several experimental tests performed on 3DW to determine their mechanical properties. In-plane properties are evaluated by tensile, compressive and in-plane shear tests, while out-of-plane properties are evaluated by short-beam shear tests and double cantilever beam tests. While Stig and Hallström [5] focused on comparing 3DW to other materials, this study is more focused on investigating the weave architecture's influence on the mechanical properties. This is achieved by varying the amount of fibres in the through-thickness direction and the warp crimp in the tested material.

2 MATERIAL

Six carbon fibre preforms (beams) were woven in a 3D-weaving loom, fully interlacing the warp with the horizontal and vertical weft, as seen in Figure 1. In the preforms, Toho Tenax HTS40 fibres were used with 12k (2x6k) yarns in the warp and 6k yarns in the horizontal weft. In the vertical weft 6k yarns were used in beams denoted 1:x and 3k yarns in beams denoted 2:x. The preforms were impregnated with RTM6 epoxy and cut, grinded and milled into the final dimensions of the specimens used in the experiments.

The weaving was made from a matrix of warp yarns with 4 rows and 31 (beams x:1 and x:2) or 37 (beams x:3) columns. Horizontal weft was picked at every warp row and vertical weft was picked at every third warp column. The weaving pattern is illustrated in Figure 2.

The beams were woven with different weave compaction, resulting in different wavelength of the warp. Specifications of the beams, including fibre volume fractions of warp and horizontal- and vertical wefts, $v_{f,wa}$, $v_{f,hwe}$, $v_{f,vwe}$, respectively, are given in Table 1. Volume fractions were also calculated from measurements on the dry preforms and the final composite materials.

Figure 1. A unit cell of the 3D-weave with blue warp yarns, red horizontal weft yarns and green vertical weft yarns. The coordinate system used in the presentation is also illustrated.

Figure 2. Weaving pattern of the preforms, view along the warp.

The warp crimp is here defined as the ratio between the yarn length and the weave length. Since only every third warp is picked with a vertical weft the warp will have different crimp depending on if it is interlaced with a vertical weft (3D) or not (2D), see Figure 1. The yarn length was not continuously measured during weaving but determined a posteriori from yarns that were pulled out from preforms and measured. Due to limited excess material from manufacturing, detailed crimp measurements were only performed for beams 1:1 and 2:2. For the other beams, the crimp was approximated from lengths of sine- (2D) and helix- (3D) functions fitted to the measurements on the specimens.

Beam	Warp wavelength [mm]	Warp crimp (2D / 3D)	Vertical weft yarn	ν_f [-]	Fibre fraction $w_a / h_{we} / v_{we}$ [-]	Fibre distribution $w_a / h_{we} / v_{we}$ [%]
1:1	14	1.006 / 1.013	6k	0.469	0.412 / 0.034 / 0.023	87.8 / 7.2 / 4.9
1:2	11	1.011 / 1.021	6k	0.482	0.414 / 0.043 / 0.025	85.9 / 8.9 / 5.2
1:3	9.6	1.015 / 1.030	6k	0.482	0.407 / 0.049 / 0.027	84.3 / 10.2 / 5.5
2:1	9.7	1.025 / 1.049	3k	0.484	0.422 / 0.049 / 0.013	87.2 / 10.1 / 2.7
2:2	9.5	1.029 / 1.051	3k	0.486	0.423 / 0.050 / 0.013	87.0 / 10.2 / 2.8
2:3	9.1	1.028 / 1.056	3k	0.479	0.413 / 0.052 / 0.013	86.3 / 10.9 / 2.8

Table 1. Specifications of the beams.

3 EXPERIMENTS

3.1 Tensile tests

Tensile tests were performed to determine the tensile ultimate strength, $\hat{\sigma}_{xx}^t$, Young's modulus, E_{xx} , and the in-plane and out-of-plane Poisson's ratios, ν_{xy} and ν_{xz} . The procedure followed the AITM 1-007 standard for plain specimens [6]. Five specimens, all having a thickness of 4 mm, were tested in a Schenk Hydropuls PSB 250 hydraulic testing machine and the load was measured with a 250 kN load cell.

An extensometer, with a 50 mm gauge length, was used to measure the displacement along the specimens. A GOM Aramis 5M Rev. 02 Digital Image Correlation (DIC) system was also used for strain measurements, with one camera monitoring the front side (xy -plane) and one camera monitoring the short side (xz -plane) of the specimen. The DIC system was used to evaluate both ν_{xy} and ν_{xz} .

3.1.1 Results and discussion

Figure 3 shows a plot of stress versus average strain from the DIC system, evaluated in the loading direction. Images of all specimens after failure are also shown in Figure 3. All specimens showed a linear stress vs. strain behaviour initially, but deviated some from linearity at higher stress levels. This correlates well with previous work [5]. Table 2 shows the results from the tensile tests in terms of Young's modulus and Poisson's ratios, evaluated between 0.1 % and 0.3 % strain. Results from the extensometer and the DIC system correlate well. The in-plane Poisson's ratio is higher than the out-of-plane ratio, which is reasonable due to the larger amount of fibres in the horizontal weft than in the vertical weft.

Figure 3. Left: Stress vs. strain curves from the tensile tests. Right: Photographs of the tested specimens.

Specimen no.	Beam	$\hat{\epsilon}_{xx}^t$ [%]	$\hat{\sigma}_{xx}^t$ [MPa]	E_{ext} [GPa]	E_{dic} [GPa]	ν_{xy} [-]	ν_{xz} [-]
1	1:1	1.07	928.75	86.82	83.91	0.22	0.45
2	1:2	1.12	860.09	78.93	86.69	0.25	0.40
3	2:1	1.13	782.82	74.66	76.23	0.17	0.22
4	2:1	1.19	853.96	81.39	80.22	0.22	0.32
5	2:2	1.13	821.59	77.21	79.58	0.22	0.55

Table 2. Material properties derived from the tensile test results.

Figure 4 shows the stiffness and strength plotted against the warp crimp. A trend is seen in that the stiffness and strength increase with lower crimp, and the strength to a larger extent than the stiffness. This was also reported by Stig and Hallström [7] and is assumed to be a result of the warp yarns with higher crimp being partly straightened and not only stretched when loaded. Straightening of yarns would show by the stress-strain curves deviating from linearity, which is clearly seen in Figure 3 where specimens with higher crimp (3, 4 and 5) deviate from linearity earlier than specimens with lower crimp (1 and 2).

Figure 4. Strength and Young's modulus vs. warp crimp. The blue circles represents the strength and the red circles represents the modulus.

3.2 Compression tests

Compression tests were performed to determine the compressive strength $\hat{\sigma}_{xx}^c$, the stiffness E_{xx} and the in-plane and out-of-plane Poisson's ratios ν_{xy} and ν_{xz} . Ten specimens, with a thickness of 3.9 mm, were tested in an ITRI-rig following the AITM standard for plain specimens [8]. The specimens were tested in an Instron 4505 universal test machine with a 100 kN load cell. The strain was measured by three strain gauges (HBM K-LY4-1-09-350-3-2) with 9 mm gauge length, two of them measuring longitudinal strain (x -direction) and one measuring transverse strain (y -direction).

One edge of the specimens (in the xz -plane) was also monitored and analysed with the DIC system. The DIC monitoring was intended to spot out-of-plane displacement and enable measurements of ν_{xz} .

3.2.1 Results and discussion

Strain measurements in compression tests are known to be challenging, which was also confirmed in these tests. Neither strain gauges nor DIC provided fully reliable measurements. Therefore, the stiffness evaluation from the compression tests was ruled out, which leaves the compressive strength as the only result from the tests. The strength results are presented in Table 3.

As in the tensile tests correlation between the strength and the warp crimp was apparent and even more so than in tension. Figure 5 presents the compressive strength vs. crimp, showing that the compressive strength decreases significantly with increasing crimp.

Beam	Number of specimens	$\hat{\sigma}_{xx}^c$ [MPa]
1:1	2	357.73 ± 10.48
1:2	3	331.09 ± 14.11
2:1	2	248.10 ± 22.92
2:2	3	252.95 ± 4.20

Table 3. Strength results from the compression tests.

Figure 5. Compressive strength vs. warp 3D-crimp.

3.3 In-plane shear tests

It was not feasible to produce large enough 3D-woven preforms for standardised in-plane shear (IPS) test specimens. Therefore, a new purpose-built test specimen was used to determine the in-plane shear strength $\hat{\tau}$. The specimens included not only 3D-woven preforms but also 2D glass fibre- and carbon weaves. The 3D-weave was used in the gauge area, while the rest of the specimens contained glass fibre reinforcement, just to make them large enough for testing. Carbon fibre 2D-weave was used to keep the specimens together during testing. The test area was then defined by milling off the 2D material locally. An illustration of the specimen geometry is shown in Figure 6.

A total of 20 specimens were tested, half of them with the shear load perpendicular to the warp and the other half with the shear load perpendicular to the horizontal weft. The approach made it possible to measure $\hat{\tau}_{xy}$ and $\hat{\tau}_{yx}$ independently of each other. The specimens had the shape and dimensions shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Dimensions of the in-plane shear specimens [mm]. Left: Specimen configuration for shear across the horizontal weft. Middle: Specimen configuration for shear across the warp. Right: Side view.

When the specimen is loaded, the gauge area is affected by shear stress and the shear strength is calculated as

$$\hat{\tau} = \frac{\hat{P}}{2 \cdot l_{gauge} \cdot t_{gauge}}, \quad (1)$$

where \hat{P} is the maximum load and l_{gauge} and t_{gauge} are the length and thickness of the gauge area, respectively.

The specimens were loaded in an Instron 5567 universal test machine and the load was measured with a 30 kN load cell. A GOM Aramis 5M Rev. 02 system (DIC) was used to evaluate the shear strain in the gauge area, at one side of the specimen.

3.3.1 Results and discussion

Evaluation of the shear strength was performed differently for the specimens depending on in what direction the shear load was applied. Figure 7 shows two shear stress vs. strain plots; one from a specimen with shear load perpendicular to the horizontal weft (left), and one from a specimen with shear load perpendicular to the warp (right). As seen there is a clear peak value $\hat{\tau}_{xy}$ before the shear stress drops in the left hand plot, but not in the right hand plot. Determining $\hat{\tau}_{yx}$ in the latter case is somewhat ambiguous, since no distinct peak value exists, and the following procedure was adopted for consistency. Two straight lines were fitted to the initial linear region and to the second linear region, after the first decline, as illustrated in Figure 7 (right). The maximum shear strain was then assumed to be where these polynomials intersect and $\hat{\tau}_{yx}$ was read out as the shear stress from the test at that strain. As can be seen in Figure 7 the result appears to be relatively conservative.

Figure 7. Shear stress-strain curves for specimens with shear across the horizontal weft (left) and with shear across the warp (right). The shear strength is indicated in both plots.

The ultimate shear strength from the valid tests are shown in Table 4. It is seen that it is higher across the warp than across the horizontal weft ($\hat{\tau}_{yx} > \hat{\tau}_{xy}$). This is attributed to the considerably higher yarn content in the warp than in the horizontal weft direction. A trend is also seen in Table 4 that 2:x beams show slightly higher shear strength than 1:x beams. The difference is however not statistically sound.

Loading direction	Beam	Number of valid failed specimens	$\hat{\tau}_{xy}$ [MPa]	$\hat{\tau}_{yx}$ [MPa]
Warp	1:3	5	46.36 ± 1.39	-
	2:3	5	48.01 ± 2.92	-
Horizontal weft	1:3	1	-	56.05
	2:3	4	-	62.15 ± 3.30

Table 4. Results from the in-plane shear tests.

3.4 Short beam shear tests

Short beam shear (SBS) tests were performed to determine the out-of-plane shear strength $\hat{\tau}_{xz}$ (ILSS)¹. The tests followed the ASTM D2344 standard [9] with some deviations stated below. The geometry and dimensions of the specimens are shown in Figure 8. According to the standard, the diameters of the loading and supporting rollers, d_l and d_s , should be 6 and 3 mm, respectively. However, other studies claim that larger rollers should be used in order to avoid local indentation failure

¹ The abbreviation refers to “inter-laminar shear strength”, although the 3DW is not a laminate.

underneath the loading roller [1]. Therefore the ASTM requirements on roller diameter were used for half of the specimens, and $d_l = 10$ mm and $d_s = 5$ mm, were used for the other half.

Figure 8. Dimensions [mm] of the short beam shear test specimens.

The specimens were loaded until complete failure in an Instron 5567 test machine and the load was measured with a 30 kN load cell. 20 specimens were prepared and tested, all cut along the warp direction.

In four of the tests a GOM Aramis 5M Rev. 02 Digital Image Correlation (DIC) system was used to study the growth of the shear strain field on one side of the specimen. The rest of the tests were recorded with a standard video camera.

An attempt was also made to test the out-of-plane shear strength in the horizontal weft direction, $\hat{\tau}_{yz}$, but since the horizontal weft only constituted about 7-11 % of the total reinforcement, such specimens failed in bending rather than in shear.

3.4.1 Results and discussion

Table 5 shows the ILSS from the short beam shear tests. Beams 1:x, with more relatively reinforcement through the thickness, were expected to show a higher ILSS than beams 2:x. It is seen in Table 5 that more reinforcement through the thickness increases the ILSS just slightly, but not very much. The spread is also considerably higher for specimens with 6k vertical weft than for the ones with 3k vertical weft.

Beam	Number of specimens	ILSS [MPa]
1:1	4	89.52 ± 13.53
1:2	6	78.94 ± 7.19
2:1	4	72.11 ± 5.58
2:2	6	80.40 ± 3.49

Table 5. Results from short beam shear tests.

The specimen size was chosen according to the standard. In the specimens that were tested in this study the weaving pattern is repeated just twice. It then becomes an issue how the specimens were cut with respect to the weave pattern, and where and how the vertical wefts are oriented and positioned in the relatively small sample. The fact that specimens with larger yarn wavelengths show larger spread than the ones with smaller wavelengths indicates that this influence is important. Using larger specimens would probably reduce these uncertainties but increasing the length of the specimens would also increase the tendency for bending failure. An alternative would be to only increase the width of the specimens.

Using larger roller diameters than required in the standard does not seem to affect the ILSS for the tested material. Some specimens that were tested with the smaller rollers showed signs of local indentation but the major failure mechanism was judged to be shear for all specimens. The vertical weft fibres increase the out of plane strength and should hence reduce the risk of local indentation and compression failure at the rollers, which could explain that no effect of the roller size was seen.

3.5 Double cantilever beam tests

Double cantilever beam (DCB) tests were performed to determine the opening mode I energy release rate G_{Ic} . The ASTM standard D5528 [10] was used as guideline throughout the tests. However, the standard is developed and intended for unidirectional 2D-layered composites, having poor out-of-plane properties. 3DW on the contrary, has better out of plane properties due to the presence of the vertical weft. Therefore, the setup proposed in the standard created problems, such as bending failure of the specimen arms, failure in the bond between the tab material and the specimen, and failure between hinges and specimens. The final setup had tab material bonded to both sides of the specimen to increase the thickness and avoid bending failure. The hinges were bonded to the tabs and screws were used to further secure their fastening to the tabs and the 3DW material. The hinges were flipped horizontally to avoid peeling stresses at the hinge-tab interfaces. Stainless steel hinges were used in the tests and the width of the specimens was adjusted to match the width of the hinges.

Five specimens were prepared and tested in an Instron 5567 test machine and the load was measured with a 5 kN load cell. After each load cycle the crack length was measured using a travelling microscope on one side of the specimen and without microscope on the opposite side, checking for uneven crack propagation. The load was increased until a distinct crack propagation of >5 mm was observed. Then the crack length was noted and the load reduced to zero. The procedure was repeated until the crack had propagated all through the specimens.

3.5.1 Results and discussion

G_{Ic} was calculated for each load cycle and crack increment using the modified beam theory described in the standard [10]. A RMS-value, $G_{Ic,rms}$, was calculated from all G_{Ic} -values, as presented in Table 6. It should be noted that specimens 1 and 4 showed uneven crack propagation and for specimen 6 the crack propagation was only measured from one side.

The results show that specimens from beams 1:x, with twice as much vertical weft as beams 2:x, show a fracture toughness that is more than twice as high than for beams 2:x. The amount of reinforcement in the vertical weft is apparently of great importance for the fracture toughness.

Beam	Specimen	$G_{Ic,rms} \pm \text{std. dev. [J/m}^2\text{]}$	Notes
1:2	1	9693 ± 931	Uneven crack propagation
1:2	1	7445 ± 991	
2:1	1	3388 ± 295	Uneven crack propagation
2:2	1	3462 ± 441	
2:2	1	3728 ± 460	Crack propagation only measured on one side

Table 6. Results from DCB test.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Composite specimens containing 3D-woven reinforcement were tested in order to characterise their mechanical properties, focusing on the influence from the weave architecture. Several previously obtained results were confirmed and some new ones were found.

The tensile and compressive properties depend greatly on warp crimp, in agreement with conclusions from earlier studies [7].

A new in-plane shear test method was used. It showed differences in the in-plane shear strength correlated with the different fibre content in the warp and horizontal weft directions.

The interlaminar shear strength appears to increase marginally with higher fibre content in the vertical weft.

The double cantilever beam tests were a challenge to perform successfully since the through thickness reinforcement increased the fracture toughness considerably causing problems with the test setup and tendencies for premature failure in other modes than the desired one. Several modifications were made to the setup recommended in the standard in order to increase the strength of the load

introductions and extract the desired properties from the specimens. As expected, the out-of-plane properties are to a large extent dependent on the size of the vertical weft yarns. Doubling the amount of fibres in the vertical weft pretty much doubles the out-of-plane fracture toughness.

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